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Research Article

**A REVIEW ON ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES FOR
DETERMINATION OF PROTON PUMP INHIBITORS****K. Vamsi¹, S. Thasneem², K.V. Nanda Kumar³, K. Venugopal⁴**

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Article Received: October 2024 Accepted: November 2024 Published: December 2024**Abstract:**

Proton Pump Inhibitors (PPIs) are a class of drugs widely used to manage conditions caused by excessive gastric acid production. They work by reducing stomach acid secretion, providing relief from symptoms of chronic acid reflux, gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), and stomach ulcers. The primary drugs in this category include omeprazole, lansoprazole, pantoprazole, esomeprazole, rabeprazole, Dex rabeprazole, dexmoprazole, and liarozole. Analytical methods for these drugs primarily involve spectroscopy and chromatography techniques. Spectroscopy methods focus on parameters like the technique used, concentration range, recovery percentage, maximum wavelength (λ_{max}), and limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ). Chromatographic techniques, such as RP-HPLC, UPLC, UFLC, LCMS/MS, RP-UPLC, and HPLC, are validated using parameters like column type, mobile phase composition, injection volume, flow rate, retention time, detector type, wavelength, recovery, linear range, correlation coefficient (R^2), LOD, and LOQ. These analytical techniques ensure the quality, safety, and efficacy of PPIs.

Keywords: *Proton Pump Inhibitors, Gastric acid production, Chronic acid reflux, Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease, Stomach ulcers, Spectroscopy, Chromatography*

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INTRODUCTION:

PPIs are one of the most prescribed class of drugs today and are used for patients with an array of gastroenterological conditions that include gastroesophageal reflux, peptic ulcer disease, Helicobacter pylori infection, and Barrett's oesophagus. Since their introduction in 1989, use of PPIs in adults doubled from 3.9% in 1999 to 7.8% in 2012. PPIs act on the gastric acid production by inhibition of the gastric H⁺/K⁺-ATPase via covalent binding to cysteine residue of this proton pump, affecting the final step of acid production. They are the most potent antagonist of gastric acid production. Six PPIs are approved by the Food & Drug Administration (FDA): Omeprazole, Lansoprazole, Dex lansoprazole, Esomeprazole, Pantoprazole, and Rabeprazole. Omeprazole, Esomeprazole, and Lansoprazole are currently available over the counter in the United States. For the otolaryngologist, PPIs are commonly used to treat laryngopharyngeal reflux (LPR). LPR is often diagnosed based on clinical findings, symptoms, and flexible laryngoscopy findings. Careful assessment of key laryngeal findings can be quite useful to guide therapy. However, some of the more commonly utilized findings are also found in otherwise normal, volunteers.[1][2]

PPIs are among the most commonly prescribed medications today, used to treat a wide range of gastroenterological conditions, including gastroesophageal reflux, peptic ulcer disease, Helicobacter pylori infection, and Barrett's Esophagus. Since their introduction in 1989, the use of PPIs in adults has significantly increased, doubling from 3.9% in 1999 to 7.8% in 2012 (1). PPIs inhibit gastric acid production by targeting the gastric H⁺/K⁺-ATPase enzyme, forming a covalent bond with its cysteine residue, thereby blocking the final step of acid production. This mechanism makes PPIs the most potent antagonists of gastric acid secretion. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has approved six PPIs: omeprazole, lansoprazole, Dex lansoprazole, esomeprazole, pantoprazole, and rabeprazole. Of these, omeprazole, esomeprazole, and lansoprazole are available over-the-counter in the United States. In otolaryngology, PPIs are often used to manage laryngopharyngeal reflux (LPR), a condition diagnosed based on symptoms, clinical findings, and flexible laryngoscopy results. While careful assessment of laryngeal findings can guide therapy, some commonly observed findings may also occur in asymptomatic, healthy individuals, necessitating a nuanced approach to diagnosis and treatment.[3][4]

Although impedance or pH testing are considered the

gold standard diagnostic tools and can be used to increase the diagnosis reliability, these techniques are not widely used in the initial diagnosis of LPR due to cost, complexity of the technique and discomfort for the patient. Primary care physicians and otolaryngologists alike commonly prescribe PPIs as an empiric therapy for LPR symptoms with variable accuracy. In some cases, this empiric treatment can also act as a diagnostic tool. Apart from the economic burden associated with the use of PPIs in the general population, concerns continue to surface regarding their use and potential complications such as bone fracture, dementia, cardiac event, renal dis ease, or infection. As the number of reports and press coverage related to the epidemiologic studies looking at the risk of PPIs increases, discussions about their potential risks are a weekly if not daily occurrence in otolaryngology outpatient client.[5][6]

Mechanism of action:

PPIs, or polypyridine sulfonamides, block the gastric proton pump by irreversibly blocking the triphosphate enzyme mechanism. They form weakly basic bases at blood pH 7.4 and are ionized only in the parietal cell's highly acidic conditions. When administered as an inactive agent, the drug forms unionized weak bases in the blood and crosses the cell membrane into the canaliculi due to its lipophilic nature. The drug then reorganizes into the active form, attaching covalently to the proton pump's cysteine residue, inhibiting further HCl secretion.

PPIs have a long action duration depending on cell generation.[7]

Adverse effects of PPIs:

PPI drug-related adverse drug reactions (ADR) can be categorized into two forms: those related to acid inhibition and those unrelated. Long-term administration of PPI can lead to adverse effects like allergic reactions, chronic kidney disease, diabetes, heart disease, and migraines, while acid inhibition-related adverse effects include diarrhea, gastric cancer, iron deficiency, bone fractures, and other health issues.[8]

Omeprazole:

Omeprazole (OPZ) is a racemate with a tricoordinate sulfinyl sulfur in a pyramidal structure. It is absorbed quickly with a peak plasma focus within 1-2 hours after ingestion of a single oral remedial portion of 20 mg. Its bioavailability is around 30-40%, increasing on repeated dosing. OPZ is highly soluble in non-aqueous solvents, easily soluble in ethanol and methanol, partially soluble in acetone and isopropanol, and very slightly soluble in water.

Various analytical methods are used to evaluate or plasma. [9,10]
quantitatively estimate OPZ in formulation or blood

TABLE-1: Chromatography techniques for determination of Omeprazole

Drug	Method	Technique	Concentration Range	Recovery	λ max	LOD&LOQ
Omeprazole	Spectroscopic method	UV	20-110 μ g/mL	100.22%	390nm	5.21 μ g/mL 15.79 μ g/mL
	Spectroscopic method	UV	5-70 μ g/mL	99.17%	301.8nm	0.6176 μ g/mL 1.8716 μ g/mL

TABLE-2: UV-visible spectroscopy techniques for the determination of OPZ

Drug Name	Technique	Column	Mobile phase	Injection volume	Flow rate	Retention time	Detection	Wavelength	Recovery	Linear range	R ²	LOD&LOQ
Omeprazole	RP-HPLC	C-18	Acetonitrile phosphate	20 μ L	0.5ML/min	10min	U.V detection	302nm	100.95%	25-175%	0.998	2.44 μ g/ml 7.33 μ g/ml
	UPLC	C-18	Acetonitrile phosphate	1 μ L	1ML/min	1.2min	U.V detection	305nm	99.19%	25-100%	0.999	1.65 μ g/ml 3.883 μ g/ml

Pantoprazole:

PPZ is classified as an irreversible blocker of the proton pump (H^+/K^+ -ATPase), specifically identified as 5-difluoromethoxybenzimidazole-2-yl 3,4-dimethoxy-2-pyridylmethyl sulfoxide (MW-383.4). The affinity of cytochrome P450 for PPZ is lower compared to that for OPZ. The metabolism of PPZ occurs in the liver through the cytochrome P450 (CYP) system, regardless of whether it is administered intravenously or orally. The primary metabolic pathway involves demethylation by CYP2C19, followed by sulfation. Additionally, oxidation via CYP3A4 represents another metabolic route. These metabolic processes lead to the formation of inactive metabolites. PPZ exhibits enhanced aqueous solubility, indicating a higher free water solubility. In comparison to omeprazole and lansoprazole, PPZ demonstrates reduced chemical stability in neutral to mildly acidic environments; however, it generates active species under strongly acidic conditions, which may influence the eradication of *H. pylori* infections. Various analytical techniques have been documented for the assessment or quantitative estimation of PPZ in formulations or blood plasma, including UV-visible spectrophotometry, HPLC, and UPLC.[12][13]

TABLE-3 : U.V Visible Spectroscopic Methods for Pantoprazole

Drug	Method	Technique	Concentration Range	Recovery	λ max	LOD&LOQ
pantoprazole	Spectrophotometry method	UV	5-70 μ g/mL	99%	292nm	3.65 μ g/mL 12.67 μ g/mL
	Spectroscopic method	UV	30-300 μ g/mL	100.6%	455nm	3.65 μ g/mL 12.67 μ g/mL

Table-4: Chromatography Techniques For Determination Of Pantoprazole

Drug Name	Technique	Column	Mobile phase	Injection volume	Flow rate	Retention time	Detector	Wavelength	Recovery	Linear range	R ²	LOD&LOQ
Pantoprazole	RP-HPLC	C-18	Ammonium acetate & methanol	20µl	1.0ML/min	8.10min	FDA detector	280nm	99.07%	3.06-1243µg/ml	0.999	1.165µg/ml 3.883µg/ml
	UFLC	C-8	Acetonitrile & Methanol	20µL	1.2ML/min	2.62min	FDA detector	252nm	96.2%	5-50µg/ml	0.992	5µg/ml 7.2µg/ml
	LC-MS/MS	C18	Water: acetonitrile	10µL	1.6ML/min	4.540min	PDA detector	282nm	79.8404%	1-500ng/ml	0.999	1.0ng/ml

TABLE-5 : U.V Visible spectroscopic determination of Rabeprazole

Drug	Method	Technique	Concentration Range	Recovery	max	LOD&LOQ
Rabeprazole	Spectrometric method	U. V	4.08-24.5 µg/mL	100.45%	284nm	0.194 µg/mL 0.832 µg/mL
	Spectrophotometric method	U. V	14-40 µg/mL	100%	470nm	0.194 µg/mL 0.832µg/mL

Table-6: Chromatography Techniques Determination Of Rabeprazole

Drug Name	Technique	Column	Mobile phase	Injection volume	Flow rate	Retention time	Detector	Wavelength	Recovery	Linear range	R ²	LOD&LOQ
Rabeprazole	RP-HPLC	C-18	Methanol and water	10 µL	0.9ML/min	5.6min	UV Detection	280nm	99.8%	20-60 µg/ml	1.0	2.96 µg/ml 10.1 µg/ml
	RP-UPLC	C-18	Acetonitrile and phosphate	10 µL	0.4ML/min	1.4min	UV detection	280nm	98.0%	0.03-30 µg/ml	0.999	0.02 µg/ml 0.06 µg/ml
	UPLC	C-18	Buffer and acetonitrile	5 µL	0.4ML/min	4.6min	UV detection	217nm	99%	0.1-2000ng/ml	0.999	0.000148 µg/ml 0.000496 µg/ml

1. Ilaprazole

IPZ, chemically designated as 2-[(RS)-[(4-methoxy-3-methylpyridin-2-yl) methyl] sulfinyl]5-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)-1H-benzimidazole, belongs to the class of proton pump inhibitors (PPIs). It is utilized in the treatment of dyspepsia, peptic ulcer disease, gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), and duodenal ulcers. The molecular formula of IPZ is C₁₉H₁₈N₄O₂S, with a molecular weight of 366.4 g/mol. As a substituted benzimidazole prodrug, IPZ acts as a weak base, accumulating in the acidic environment of the gastric parietal cell's secretory canaliculus, where it is converted into an active sulphenamide form. The metabolism of IPZ is primarily facilitated by the enzymes CYP3A5 and CYP2C9, as observed in healthy Chinese subjects.

Additionally, IPZ exhibits high solubility in organic solvents and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO).[19][20][21]

TABLE-7: U.V Visible spectroscopic determination of Ilaprazole

Drug	Method	Technique	Concentration Range	Recovery	λ_{max}	LOD&LOQ
Ilaprazole	Spectroscopic method	UV	2-12 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	99.7%	307nm	0.3676 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ 1.1137 $\mu\text{g/mL}$

TABLE-8: Chromatographic determination of Ilaprazole

Drug Name	Technique	Column	Mobile phase	Injection volume	Flow rate	Retention time	Detector	Wavelength	Recovery	Linear range	R ²	LOD&LOQ
Ilaprazole	HPLC	C-18	ACN and Water	20 μL	1.0ml/min	4.0min	PDA detection	305 nm	99.78%	5-15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.998	0.05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ 0.14 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
	UPLC	RP-18	ACH and MeOH and ammonium acetate buffer	10 μL	0.25ml/min	6.3min	UV detection	305nm	97.9%	0.060400 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.999	0.018 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ 0.060 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Tenatoprazole:

The molecular formula of TPZ is C₁₆H₁₈N₄O₃S, with a molecular weight of 346.4 g/mol. TPZ, or 3-methoxy-8-[(4-methoxy-3,5-dimethyl-pyridin-2-yl)methyl sulfinyl] 2,7,9-triazabicyclo [4.3.0] nona-2,4,8,10-tetraene, functions as a prodrug within the proton pump inhibitor (PPI) class. It undergoes conversion to its active forms, sulphenamide or sulfenic acid, in the acidic environment of the

secretory canaliculus of stimulated gastric parietal cells. The active compound subsequently binds to cysteine residues that are accessible within the lumen of the gastric H⁺K⁺-ATPase, leading to the formation of disulfide bonds and the inhibition of acid secretion. The half-life of TPZ has been documented to be 3.9 hours. Similar to other PPIs, TPZ exhibits solubility in organic solvents and sodium hydroxide, among other substances.[22][23][24]

TABLE-9: U.V Visible spectroscopic determination of Tenatoprazole

Drug	Method	Technique	Concentration Range	Recovery	λ_{max}	LOD&LOQ
Tenatoprazole	Spectroscopic method	UV	2-12 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	99.37%	314nm	0.0866 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ 0.2625 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
	Spectrometric calibration curve method	UV	0-50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	99.37%	314nm	0.9882 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ 1.9482 $\mu\text{g/mL}$

TABLE-10: Chromatographic Determination of Tenatoprazole

Drug Name	Technique	Column	Mobile phase	Injection volume	Flow rate	Retention time	Detector	Wavelength	Recovery	Linear range	R ²	LOD&LOQ
Tenatoprazole	RP-HPLC	C-18	10Mm phosphate buffer and ACN	20 μL	1.0ml/min	3.54min	UV Detection	307nm	99.20%	1-6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.999	0.2515 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ 0.7623 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
	RP-HPLC	C-18	Methanol and tetrahydrofuran	20 μL	1.0ml/min	3.7min	PDA Detection	307nm	99%	0.5-160 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.999	0.49 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ 1.50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Esomeprazole:

Esomeprazole (EPZ) is primarily used in the form of esomeprazole magnesium trihydrate, with a molecular weight of 345.4 g/mol. Its chemical structure is bis(5-methoxy-2-[(S)-(4-methoxy-3,5-dimethyl-2-pyridinyl) methyl] sulfinyl]-1H-benzimidazole-1-yl) magnesium trihydrate, and its molecular formula is (C₁₇H₁₈N₃O₃S)₂. The molecular weight is 767.2 g as a trihydrate and 713.1 g in an anhydrous form. Esomeprazole is the S-isomer of omeprazole and is notable as the first single optical isomer proton pump inhibitor. Compared to racemic proton pump inhibitors, it offers superior acid control and demonstrates a more favourable pharmacokinetic profile than omeprazole.^{[25][26][27]}

The stability of EPZ magnesium is influenced by pH levels; it degrades rapidly in acidic environments but maintains acceptable stability in alkaline conditions.

At a pH of 6.8 (buffer), the half-life of the magnesium salt is approximately 19 hours at 25°C and around 8 hours at 37°C. Its bioavailability is reported to be 89%, with a plasma elimination half-life of 1.5 hours. The peak plasma concentration (C_{max}) of EPZ, following oral administration, is typically reached within 1.5 hours (t_{max}). The plasma protein binding for EPZ is roughly 97%, remaining consistent across a concentration range of 2–20 mmol/L. The drug is metabolized by the liver's cytochrome P450 (CYP) enzyme system, with about 80% of the orally administered dose excreted as inactive metabolites in urine, while the remaining inactive metabolites are found in feces. The solubility of EPZ has been documented in ethanol, methanol, and acetone, and it is slightly soluble in water. EPZ is primarily indicated for the treatment of gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), esophagitis, gastric ulcers, and other related conditions.^{[28][29][30]}

TABLE-11: Chromatographic techniques determination of Esomeprazole

Drug Name	Technique	Column	Mobile phase	Injection volume	Flow rate	Retention time	Detector	Wavelength	Recovery	Linearity	R ²	LOD&LOQ
Esomeprazole	HPLC	C-18	Methanol and acetonitrile	20 µL	1.0ml/min	6.8min	UV Detection	300nm	99.78 %	5-25 µg/ml	0.999	0.100 µg/ml 0.314 µg/ml
	UPLC	C-18	MeOH and ACN	20µL	0.7ml/min	2.4min	UV Detection	210nm	99.1 %	5-15 µg/ml	0.999	1.4 µg/ml 4.4 µg/ml

Future perspectives for analytical methodologies for analysis, and both qualitative and quantitative ppi:

As proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) are widely utilized for the treatment of various disorders, there is a growing trend towards the development and marketing of novel and enhanced formulations. Consequently, there is a need for precise and advanced analytical methodologies to analyze PPIs in bulk substances, formulations, and human biological matrices. This survey primarily highlights the use of spectrophotometric and chromatographic techniques for analysis. However, given the expanding scope of PPIs, more efficient techniques such as Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography (UPLC) and Ultra-Fast Liquid Chromatography (UFLC) are essential for accurate and rapid measurement of PPIs. Hyphenated techniques, particularly UPLC coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS), are of significant interest due to their extensive applications in impurity profiling, related substance

assessments. Additionally, techniques such as capillary zone electrophoresis and micellar electrokinetic capillary chromatography may be necessary for specific conditions or specialized products, making the availability of such methods highly valuable. Furthermore, the optimization of these methods through Design of Experiments (DoE) or Quality by Design (QbD) approaches is crucial for enhancing the reliability of PPI analyses. While analytical methods for estimating or studying the stability of PPIs have been developed and published with considerable interest, there is a pressing need to extend their applications to pharmacokinetic studies and bioequivalence assessments.^{31,32,33,34}

CONCLUSION:

Proton Pump Inhibitors (PPIs), including medications such as lansoprazole, omeprazole, pantoprazole, rabeprazole, dexlansoprazole, esomeprazole,

dexrabeprazole, ilaprazole, and tenatoprazole, play a crucial role in significantly reducing gastric acid production. These drugs are utilized in the treatment of conditions such as peptic ulcers, H. pylori infections, Zollinger–Ellison syndrome, and gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD). This review discusses various quantitative estimation techniques, including UV-Visible Spectrophotometry, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), and Ultra-Performance Liquid Chromatography (UPLC), as well as some hyphenated methods like LC-MS/MS for analyzing these compounds in both single and combination formulations, as well as in human plasma or other biological matrices. The stability-indicating methods reported are effective in separating and quantifying both the main drug and its impurities. Some of these methods were developed using Design of Experiments (DoE) or Quality by Design (QbD) approaches to optimize the analytical processes. It can be concluded that most of the methods are characterized by their simplicity, rapidity, reproducibility, and cost-effectiveness, as evidenced by their validation parameters, which include linearity, recovery, precision, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantification (LOQ), confirming their suitability for analytical applications. All HPLC and UPLC methods utilize reverse phase chromatography with UV detection, while many spectrophotometric techniques operate by reacting with a reagent or developing a color. The hyphenated techniques, particularly LC-MS/MS and UPLC-MS/MS, are predominantly employed for stability-indicating and impurity profiling analyses. Future perspectives suggest a need to adapt to emerging trends aimed at enhancing modern analytical methods for PPIs.

ABBREVIATIONS:

UV	Ultra Violet
RP	Reverse Phase
HPLC	High Performance Liquid Chromatography
UPLC	Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography
UFLC	Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography
LC-MS	Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy
PPI	Proton Pump Inhibitors LPZ, OPZ, Lansoprazole, Omeprazole, PPZ, RPZ, Pantoprazole, Rabeprazole EPZ, Esomeprazole
GIT	Gastro intestinal tract
ACN	Acetonitrile
MeOH	Methanol
LOD	Limit of Detection
LOQ	Limit of Quantitation

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